

PUBLIC DISCOURSE: SYSTEMIC FUNCTIONAL ANALYSIS OF VP SARA DUTERTE'S SPEECHES

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Public Discourse: Systemic Functional Analysis of VP Sara Duterte's Speeches

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Abstract

This study aimed to explore and unveil the linguistic features, persuasive strategies and political ideologies used in Vice President Sara Duterte's Speeches. The categories of linguistic features were referred to Finegan's Linguistic Features of Structure and Use (2008). Using a discourse analysis approach, the researcher focused on two dimensions: morphology and syntax. Twenty public speeches were gathered from YouTube. Within the domain of morphology, the study revealed that out of the twenty videos that were analyzed three (3) of them used compounding, five (5) used reduplication and four (4) used initialism. In the realm of syntax, the analysis uncovered three types of sentences: simple, compound and complex sentence. It was revealed that three of the public speeches used simple sentences, four used compound and three used complex sentences. On the other hand, persuasive strategies were referred to as Aristotle Persuasive Strategies (1983). The results of the persuasive strategies revealed that three of the videos used ethical appeal, three used logical and three used emotional appeal. Lastly, political ideologies were referred to Van Dijk Ideological Interaction Theory. It was revealed that two of the public speeches used acquired, two used expressed and two used propagated as political ideology.

Keywords: *discourse analysis, persuasive strategies, public speeches, linguistic features, political ideologies*

Introduction

Sara Duterte, the Vice President of the Philippines, has emerged as a prominent political figure in the said country, garnering attention for her leadership style and public speeches. Recently assuming the role of Vice President, Duterte's speeches carry significant weight in shaping public discourse and political narratives. Discourse analysis provides a valuable lens through which to examine the linguistic and rhetorical strategies employed by Vice President Duterte in conveying her messages to the Filipino people.

In Australia, a study by Sengul (2019) illuminates the application of critical discourse analysis (CDA) through a case study of right-wing populist discourse. The study, anchored in an empirical analysis of Australian Senator Pauline Hanson's 2016 maiden speech, serves as a practical example for communication scholars seeking to employ CDA in political contexts. By offering a detailed overview of the theoretical foundations, significant approaches, and shared tenets of critical discourse analysis, the paper contributes to the field's understanding of this valuable research methodology. It responds to the call for a deeper engagement with qualitative and critical approaches in political communication research, addressing the challenges posed by an increasingly complex media and communication environment.

Meanwhile, in the Philippines, Medriano and De Vera (2020) delve into "Dominance Construction in Monologic Political Discourse" based on selected public speeches of Vice President Sara Duterte. Anchored on Foucauldian Discourse Analysis, the study extracts discourse segments using content analysis to identify characteristics of "monologic discourse" in VP Sara's speeches. The research explores the speech acts features and rhetoric strategies embedded in these segments, employing contrastive analysis to discern patterns across varied political speech types. Notably, the findings reveal a considerable volume of monologic discourses in different speech contexts, suggesting the deliberate use of political speeches by VP Sara Duterte to convey dominance. The study underscores the consistent patterns and characteristics within VP Sara's monologic discourses, shedding light on the strategic deployment of rhetoric strategies such as ethos, logos, and pathos.

The research gap in the Philippines lies prominently in the dearth of comprehensive discourse analysis on the speeches of Vice President Sara Duterte, despite her emergence as a pivotal political figure. Existing studies, exemplified by examinations of right-wing populist discourse in Australia and dominance construction in Vice President Sara Duterte's speeches, provide valuable insights into discourse analysis methodologies. However, the focus on Vice President Sara Duterte remains limited, impeding a nuanced understanding of her linguistic and rhetorical strategies in shaping public narratives. This research gap is particularly pronounced given the unique socio-cultural and political context of the Philippines. The transition from Mayor to Vice President marks a critical juncture in Sara Duterte's political career, demanding scholarly attention to discern the evolution of her leadership style and communicative strategies. Addressing this gap is crucial for enhancing the academic discourse on Philippine politics, providing insights into how language is employed by political leaders to shape public perceptions and advance political agendas, and offering a valuable resource for scholars, policymakers, and the public seeking a deeper understanding of Filipino political discourse.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study is to unveil and comprehend the linguistic and rhetorical strategies employed by Vice President Sara Duterte in her public speeches, with a specific focus on shaping public discourse and political narratives in the Philippines. The examination aims to shed light on the persuasive techniques utilized by Vice President Duterte and identify the common linguistic features embedded

in her speeches. In this research, persuasive expression is defined as the linguistic prowess employed by Vice President Duterte to influence the attitudes and decisions of the public, thereby guiding them toward the intended direction of her political messaging. The study seeks to contribute to a nuanced understanding of how linguistic and rhetorical choices contribute to the persuasive impact of political communication, particularly in the context of Vice President Duterte's speeches.

1. What are the common linguistic features found in Vice President Sara Duterte's public speeches that contribute to the shaping of public discourse?
2. What rhetorical strategies does Vice President Duterte employ in her speeches to influence political narratives and public perceptions?
3. What ideologies can be generated from the public speeches of Vice President Sara Duterte?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a qualitative research design in a discourse analysis approach. In order to understand how people interpret and make meaning of their experiences, qualitative research emphasizes this aspect of social behavior. It allows for the usage to collect, examine, and interpret the data, content analysis of visual and textual resources and oral history. It also aims to assist us in better comprehending the social environment in which we reside and the reasons why things happen to become what they are (Mojahan, 2018).

In this study, the qualitative research design was considered the most appropriate design. Furthermore, the results of qualitative research methods are more descriptive, and the inferences can be drawn quite easily from the data that is obtained. Given that the goal of this study is to investigate and comprehend specific social phenomena from an interpretive and subjective standpoint and identify the linguistic features that were concealed in Vice President Sara Duterte's statements, a qualitative research approach is adopted.

Moreover, this study employed a discourse analysis approach. Discourse analysis is a general term for several approaches to analyze written, vocal, or sign language use, or any significant semiotic event. Contrary to much traditional linguistics, discourse analyst not only study language use 'beyond the sentence boundary' but also prefer to analyze 'naturally occurring' language use. To investigate bigger language structures, attempts are made to study how sentences and clauses are organized. Thus, it examines larger linguistics units as conversational exchanges of written or spoken texts (Abdullahi et al., 2020).

In this study, discourse analysis is utilized since discourse is the best method for interpreting the research materials. The context of language is crucial as it considers language as a social practice. Discourse analysis allowed for the exploration and analysis of how language was used. Moreover, written and spoken texts should be analyzed critically and constructively. Thus, discourse requires not only a local coherence within texts, but also an assessment of the significance or value of the global textual items within it (Sayer, 2016).

Instrument

The corpora utilized in this study are the speeches of Vice President Sarah Duterte. As such, this study utilized 20 videos of the speeches of the Vice President that was posted on the most utilized social media platforms in the Philippines – Facebook, TikTok and YouTube. The researcher employed social media because it is the usual place where individuals watch and listen to speakers. Braun and Clarke (2013) advocate for a flexible and informed approach to selecting the number of corpora in thematic analysis. As anchored, it was previously advised that in order to adequately accomplish the study's objective and achieve data saturation, the sample size for this investigation should consist of at least 10–100 research materials as references.

The transcripts were analyzed using systemic functional analysis and was then organized into categories and subcategories to identify recurring patterns and relationships between the data. The duration of each video had a minimum length of three (3) minutes and has no maximum length of time. The focus was to analyze language, comprehend the linguistic and rhetorical strategies based on what it does, rather than how it is structured. It aims to understand how language is used to achieve different communication goals in different social situation.

Procedure

The researcher used a set of procedures to carry out this investigation in a methodical manner. The investigator made certain that the procedures and moral guidelines were followed during the data collection phase. As a result, the research methodology was carefully created, with the right data collecting and sample strategies chosen. During this stage, ethical issues including informed permission, data protection, and confidentiality have to be taken into account. The researcher strictly adhered to these ethical guidelines during the whole data gathering process, guaranteeing the accuracy and authenticity of the data.

The researcher's initial action was to work with the research adviser to establish a clear understanding of the steps that needed to be taken in order to carry out this investigation. Given that the researcher had never used the discourse analysis approach before, the researcher consulted about how to analyze the gathered data and about the study's overall methodology. Moreover, it was necessary upon the researcher to possess sufficient expertise about the methodologies employed in order to guarantee the completeness and the

comprehensiveness of the investigation.

The 20 online videos of Vice President Sara Duterte's speeches served as the research corpora for this study. A purposive sample method was used for the selection to the research materials, adhering to the previously mentioned set of criteria in order to reduce the abundance of sources that were available online. The researcher made sure the videos picked had relation to the study's objective; aimed to reveal the systemic functional analysis of OVP Sara Duterte Speeches and to pinpoint the common linguistic patterns in her language use.

Data Analysis

The research materials for this study included 20 videos of Vice President Sara Duterte's speeches, which were used to explore this research. These videos were chosen based on particular standards that complemented the goals of the research. In order to fulfil the requirements and goals of this researcher's study, the data acquired was presented and carefully examined. Thus, in order to accomplish this, the researcher made use of the theoretical frameworks that were presented in the previous chapter. To answer the study questions presented in the preceding chapter, several frameworks were utilized.

The process of analyzing the corpora was hinged on the theoretical frameworks discussed in the first chapter. The theories were the Linguistic Features of Structure and Use, as proposed by Finegan (1984), Aristotle's Persuasive Strategies (Beiner, 1983), and the Ideological Interaction Theory, as conceptualized by Van Dijk (2006). Since the goal of this study was to address the research questions, the aforementioned frameworks served as a guide for the entire data analysis procedure.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical consideration ensures the responsible and humane conduct of the research. This addresses a range of issues related to the rights and well-being of participants, the integrity of research data, and the potential impact of research findings. The study was implemented with consideration for and adherence to ethical guidelines in order to guarantee appropriate practice and conduct. With this, the researcher followed ethical values in conducting the research and these are the following: respect for persons, beneficence, justice, agreement, and confidentiality (Boyatzis, 1998; Mack et al., 2005).

Respect for persons emphasizes respecting people's dignity and acknowledging their individuality. It entails valuing their preferences, convictions, and privacy. It recognizes the inherent dignity and worth of each individual and emphasizes the importance of treating research participants with respect, fairness, and autonomy. Special attention must be given to protecting the rights and well-being of vulnerable populations. Adherence to this principle ensures that people will not be used simply as a means to achieve research objectives (Mack et al., 2005).

As this study was corpora-based and did not require interviewing research participants to acquire data, this criterion was upheld by making sure that no one in the videos utilized as research material was used for non-academic reasons. Additionally, the researcher used video data in a manner that precisely complied with ethical requirements. Every video that was utilized for research was carefully chosen, and the rights and privacy of the people in the videos were respected to the fullest extent possible. This procedure preserved the participants' dignity and assisted in preserving their privacy.

Beneficence underscores that the study should be beneficial and not risky to those people who will be involved in the study (Pieper & Thomson, 2016). Its core ethical principle is to emphasize the importance of maximizing potential benefits and minimizing potential risks to participants. With this, researchers carefully consider the ethical implications of the work and to prioritize the well-being of participants above all else.

As such, the researcher takes steps to minimize risks by implementing appropriate safeguards and procedures. The study's corpora were never used in a way that would cause hurt, disdain, or degrade the people who were highlighted in the materials. To maximize benefits and minimize harm, the researcher handled the data with care and sensitivity making sure that no data files were ignored or disclosed.

Justice is an ethical principle that focuses on fairness and equity in the distribution of the burdens and benefits of the study. This may involve considering factors such as race, ethnicity, socioeconomic status, gender, and other factors that might put certain groups at increased risk or disadvantage. In order to avoid the exclusion of any certain group, the researcher must make sure that the research does not result in any unfairness or bias at any point during the study, especially when choosing research participants (Farrugia, 2019).

In this inquiry which utilizes the speeches of Vice President Sara Duterte as corpora, justice will be manifested through the fair analysis of each material. The researcher ensure that personal biases are not present in the analysis process. The way the data is handled will be determined by the study objectives and theoretical frameworks of this investigation, not by the researcher's own judgment. This guarantees the administration of justice and the triumph of fairness.

A key ethical principle in research is confidentiality, which guarantees participant's privacy and safeguards private data from unwanted publication. Encouraging people to participate in research and fostering trust between researcher and the participants both depend on this idea. When conducting research, the researcher should respect the privacy of human subjects when gathering, analyzing, and reporting data. With this, confidentiality is an ethical practice.

The selection process for corpora followed a systematic and unbiased approach, offering equal opportunity to all eligible materials that met the predefined criteria. The speeches of Vice President Sara Duterte that were included in this study are given a code to ensure anonymity. The data processing appropriately handled that only the researcher, adviser, and the panel of expert will have an access to the extent of this inquiry.

Results and Discussion

This section presented the gathered data taken from Vice President Sara Duterte’s Public Speeches. The public speeches were transcribed, scrutinized, and analyzed to identify the linguistic features, persuasive strategies and ideologies. The data that was collected to answer the three research questions; first, what are the common linguistic features found in Vice President Sara Duterte’s public speeches that contribute to the shaping of public discourse? Second, what persuasive strategies does Vice President Duterte employ in her speeches to influence political narratives and public perceptions? Third, what ideologies can be generated from the public speeches of Vice President Sara Duterte? This part of the paper presented the linguistic features Vice President Sara Duterte’s Public Speeches, particularly the morphological and syntactic features. This chapter also presented the persuasive strategies employed in the Public Speeches as well as the ideologies that can be generated from the Public Speeches.

Morphological Features in Vice President Sara Duterte’s Public Speeches

Morphology studies how words were formed and varied. It studies the relationship between morphemes, and how morphemes can be put together to create new words, or new forms of the stem word. Understanding how the words were formed enables us to unlock our vocabulary, particularly on what words we must use to create a meaningful and effective communication. The analysis was made by the researcher on the Public Speeches of Sara Duterte, and it was found out that there were three types of morphological process present in her speeches. The collected data were analyzed based on Finegan’s Lexicon and Morphological Features. The morphological features in Vice President Duterte’s Speeches were analyzed in a tabular presentation which points out different processes such as compounding, reduplication and initialisms.

In linguistic morphology, it is focused on studying words formation and how it relates to other words in language. Compounding is the process of putting words together to create new words. It joins two separate words to produce a new word in a single form. And with regards to the words present in Vice President Sara Duterte’s Speeches, different words were combined, and which produced another word with distinct meaning. In other words, it is the process of combining two or more distinct words and make it work together. Compound words were somehow confused as blended words but in compounding, the words being compound does not change in structure, blended word does.

As presented in Table 1.1, the study uncovered that Vice President Sara Duterte’s Public Speeches contained compound words or undergo the process of compounding as part of the morphological aspect. The table also included the sample words and the sample statement in which the word is used in the speech.

Research Question 1: What are the common linguistic features found in Vice President Sara Duterte’s public speeches that contribute to the shaping of public discourse?

Table 1.1.1 *Compounding in VP Sara Duterte’s Speeches*

<i>Morphological Process</i>	<i>Sample Words</i>	<i>Sample Statement</i>
Compounding	Teenage Teen - the years of the persons age from 13 to 19 Age - the length of time that a person has lived or a thing has existed Teenage – someone who is between 13 to 19 years old.	Through the promotion of alternative delivery modes, we were able to decrease the total number of dropouts due to teenage pregnancy. (PS-02) DepEd is also making sure that teenage mothers who have dropped out of formal school to take care of their children (PS-03) the failure to identify and speak up against different kinds of abuses, the life altering effects of teenage pregnancy (PS-10)
	Nationwide Nation – a large body of people united by common descent , history, culture, or language, inhabiting a particular country or territory. Wide – of great or more than average width. Nationwide – extending or reaching throughout a whole nation.	On top of this, 305 schools have been given fiber internet connectivity while satellites have been delivered to 2,000 public schools nationwide. (PS-02) we will pursue full digitization and interconnectivity of all DepEd offices and schools nationwide (PS-02) It is my earnest desire that the nationwide roll out will help stimulate entrepreneurial activities, create employment and contribute to our post pandemic recovery. (PS-03)
	Motherland Mother – a female parent of a child. Land – the solid part of the surface of the earth. Motherland – the country where you were born or where your family came from.	From our soldiers, who fight for our motherland and tirelessly protect our peace and liberty. (PS-02)

As presented in the table 1.1.1, compound words are evident in Vice President Sara Duterte’s Public Speeches. These are particularly dominant in the corpora being gathered. The compound word “teenage” which is a combination of the word “teen” and “age”, was found present in Vice President Sara Duterte’s Public Speeches, which means someone who is between 13 and 19 years old. The sentence below shown how the compounded word was utilized in the analyzed corpora.

Through the promotion of alternative delivery modes, we were able to decrease the total number of dropouts due to teenage pregnancy. (PS-02)

DepEd is also making sure that teenage mothers who have dropped out of formal school to take care of their children. (PS-03)

The failure to identify and speak up against different kinds of abuses, the life altering effects of teenage pregnancy. (PS-10)

Apart from that, the word “nationwide” which is formed by the two words “nation” and “wide” was also a compounded word which means existing or happening in all parts of a particular country, or in all parts of a particular country. It was being used in the analyzed corpora.

On top of this, 305 schools have been given fiber internet connectivity while satellites have been delivered to 2,000 public schools nationwide. (PS-02)

We will pursue full digitization and interconnectivity of all DepEd offices and schools nationwide. (PS-02)

It is my earnest desire that the nationwide roll out will help stimulate entrepreneurial activities, create employment and contribute to our post pandemic recovery. (PS-03)

Besides, the word “motherland which was created from the two different words “mother” and “land” means the country in which you were born, or the country with which you feel most connected. Sample statement from the Philippine television advertisements was stipulated below:

From our soldiers, who fight for our motherland and tirelessly protect our peace and liberty. (PS-02)

Reduplication. Another morphological process is reduplication which is a process of forming words by repeating a base morpheme, syllable, or segment- either to the right or to the left of the words, and sometimes within a word. It creates a new form with a modified meaning. It is a common feature in many languages across the world, especially in inflectional and derivational processes. In the Table 1.1.2, only full reduplication was found present in the research materials. This refers to the complete repetition of the base without any variation or alteration within the repeated portion. In other words, the entire base, whether it is a morpheme, syllable, or segment, is duplicated in its entirety. Hence, the researcher did not encounter any instances of partial reduplication, infixal reduplication, or variations in the reduplication process in the languages or words examined in the materials.

Table 1.1.2. Reduplication in VP Sara Duterte’s Speeches

Morphological Process	Sample Words	Sample Statement
Reduplication	hinding-hindi	yung trabaho ninyo and ‘ yung trabaho ng mga migrant workers ay ang isang trabahong hiding-hindi ko gustong gawin sa buhay ko.(PS-01) Kahanga-hanga po ang inyong ginagawa para sa mga kababaihan at hindi po matatawaran ang epekto ng inyong ginagawa sa mga komunidad. (PS-15)
	araw-araw	Araw-araw, iba’t-ibang hamon ang kinakaharap natin. (PS-02) ako lang ang nag-iisip araw-araw kung anong kakainin ko sa lunch (PS-17)
	iba-iba	Araw-araw, iba-ibang hamon ang kinakaharap natin. At hindi po nating tinatangi na maraming pagsubok ang dumarating sa Kagawaran ng Edukasyon. (PS-02) makikita rin nating ang iba’t-ibang mukha ng pagsisikap na naka angkla sa sinumpaang bokasyon sa pagnanais na maglingkod at sa hangaring matuoad ang mga pangarap. (PS-05)

Shown in the table is the reduplication present in the materials gathered. In the case of the term “hinding-hindi”, the reduplication of the word “hindi ” means absolutely never. The repetition of the morpheme intensifies the meaning of “hindi” which means “never” in English. Thus, “hinding-hindi” can be perceived as “absolutely never”. The term was found present in the following statements:

Yung trabaho ninyo and ‘ yung trabaho ng mga migrant workers ay ang isang trabahong hiding-hindi ko gustong gawin sa buhay ko.(PS-01)

(Your job and the job of migrant workers is the one job I would never want to do in my life.)

Kahanga-hanga po ang inyong ginagawa para sa mga kababaihan at hindi po matatawaran ang epekto ng inyong ginagawa sa mga komunidad. (PS-15)

(What you are doing for women is amazing and the impact of what you are doing on the communities is immeasurable)

In addition, “araw-araw” was also a reduplicated word found in the material. It is comparable to the previous one, but it has a different

meaning and use. When the word “araw,” which means “day” or “is reduplicated as “araw-araw,” it now conveys the idea of every day. The reduplication “araw-araw” was utilized in the statements below:

“Araw-araw, iba’t-ibang hamon ang kinakaharap natin.” (PS-02)

(Every day, we face different challenges.)

“Ako lang ang nag-iisip araw-araw kung anong kakainin ko sa lunch” (PS-17)

(I’m the only one who thinks every day what I’m going to eat for lunch)

Moreover, the reduplication “iba-iba” was also found present in public speeches of VP Sara Duterte. The repeated word “iba” in the Filipino language is frequently used to denote difference. Therefore, “iba-iba” highlights the degree or level of differences. The term was found present in the following statements:

Araw-araw, iba-ibang hamon ang kinakaharap natin. At hindi po nating tinatangi na maraming pagsubok ang dumarating sa Kagawaran ng Edukasyon. (PS-2)

(Every day, we face different challenges. And we do not deny that many challenges are coming to the Department of Education.)

Makikita rin nating ang iba’t-ibang mukha ng pagsisikap na naka angkla sa sinumpaang bokasyon sa pagnanais na maglingkod at sa hangaring matuoad ang mga pangarap. (PS-5)

(We can also see the different faces of effort anchored in the sworn vocation in the desire to serve and in the desire to make dreams come true.)

As displayed in table 1.1.3, the study found that the Public Speeches of Vice President Sara Duterte utilized initialisms as morphological aspect in presenting their ideas and messages. The table shown morphological process and its sample words. Shown also in the table was the sample statements from Public Speeches of Vice President Sara Duterte as the corpora where the initialisms found, were also presented.

Table 1.1.3. *Initialism in VP Sara Duterte’s Speeches*

<i>Morphological Process</i>	<i>Sample Words</i>	<i>Sample Statement</i>
Initialism	S + Y S – school Y – year School year refers to another term for academic year. P + Q + F P - Philippine Q - Qualification F – Framework Philippine Qualifications Framework is a national policy which describes the levels of educational qualifications and sets the standards for qualification outcomes. A + L + S A – Alternative L – Learning S – System ALS is a parallel learning system in the Philippines that provides a practical option to the existing formal instruction. N + P + A N – New P – People’s A – Army NPA is the Communist Party of the Philippines (CCP) and its armed wing. R + O + T + C R - Reserve O – Officers’ T - Training C – Corps ROTC a leadership training and development program that prepares full-time, college-enrolled students for service opportunities in the Army, Marine Corps, Navy, Air Force and Space Force.	We are actively monitoring the pilot run determine areas may need enhancements before its nationwide implementation in S.Y 2024-2025. (PS-02) We have included junior high school and senior high school diplomas in the PQF levels 1 and 2 which will help increase the employability of our senior high school graduates. (PS-02) We have also taken the initiative to develop an alternative learning system or ALS micro certification advocacy and communication plan complete with ready to use materials for ALS learners. (PS-02) Make sure that they can enroll in ALS they can enroll in an open university. (PS-03) Taong 2017, personal kong nakita na nag-aagaw buhay sa hospital ang isang biktima ng pinasabog na Improvised Explosive Device ng mga NPA, sa Mandog, Davao City. (PS-16) Let us honor the memories of those who died in the senseless and bloody attacks of the NPA. (PS-16) Not just in basic education but in higher education and ano po ‘yung mga ways forward namin to give meet doon sa declaration ng ating Pangulo na ibalik ang ROTC as a mandatory requirement for citizens. (PS-04)

Initialisms. Some shortenings resemble acronyms but are pronounced as a sequence of letters. Initialisms is another type of morphological process which are of very similar to acronyms because they are also created by taking the initial letters of a set of words and compounding them to one form. As presented on Table 1.1.3, five terms were founded present in the Public Speeches of Vice President Sara Duterte. These are “SY”, “PQF”, “ALS”, “NPA” and “ROTC”.

The initialism “SY” or School Year means academic year. In the Public Speeches gathered, the term “SY” was utilized as the sample statements stipulated below:

We are actively monitoring the pilot run determine areas may need enhancements before its nationwide implementation in S.Y. 2024-2025. (PS-02)

On the other hand, another initialism founded in Vice President Sara Duterte’s Public Speeches is “PQF” which stands for Philippine Qualification Framework. PQF describes the levels of educational qualifications and sets the standards for qualification outcomes. The term PQF was stipulated in the statement below:

We have included junior high school and senior high school diplomas in the PQF levels 1 and 2 which will help increase the employability of our senior high school graduates. (PS-02)

Nonetheless, another initialism present in Vice President Sara Duterte’s Public Speeches is “ALS” which stands for Alternative Learning System. ALS or Alternative Learning System is a parallel learning system in the Philippines that provides a practical option to the existing formal instruction.

We have also taken the initiative to develop an alternative learning system or ALS micro certification advocacy and communication plan complete with ready to use materials for ALS learners. (PS-02)

Make sure that they can enroll in ALS they can enroll in an open university. (PS-03)

Another initialism founded in Philippine television advertisements is the “NPA” which means New People’s Army. It has been observed in Vice President Sara Duterte’s Public Speeches which means the Communist Party of the Philippines (CCP) and its armed wing. The sample statement taken from the corpora was stated below:

Let us honor the memories of those who died in the senseless and bloody attacks of the NPA. (PS-16)

Furthermore, the term “ROTC” is also used in Vice President Sara Duterte’s Public Speeches which means the Reserve Officers Training Corps (ROTC). ROTC is tasked to train and develop college students in the rudiments of Military Service in order to produce capable Armed Forces of the Philippines reservists. The sample statement taken from the corpora was stated below:

Not just in basic education but in higher education and ano po ‘yung mga ways forward namin to give meet doon sa declaration ng ating Pangulo na ibalik ang ROTC as a mandatory requirement for citizens. (PS-04)

Table 1.2 reveals that Vice President Sara Duterte’s Public Speeches presented syntactic features. The Public Speeches of Sara Duterte as corpora commonly used simple, compound and complex sentences. To have a clear understanding, the first column presents the types of sentence clause structure. The last column was the Public Speeches of Vice President Sara Duterte sample statements with its code.

To have a clear understanding, the first column presents the types of sentence clause structure. The last column was the Public Speeches of Vice President Sara Duterte that contained and used each type of sentence clause structure to be easily understood.

A clause is a set of words that makes up a sentence. It consists of a subject and a predicate. It can also be said that a clause should have a subject and a verb. A subject is the word that identifies the topic of a sentence or who is doing the activity and those were the words written in bold text while the underline word was the verb.

Table 1.2. Syntactic Features of VP Sara Duterte’s Speeches

<i>Types of Sentences</i>	<i>Sample Statements</i>
Simple Sentence	Education is everybody's business. (PS-02) Today is a timely opportunity to renew our call to everyone. (PS-06) We must prioritize peace and order. (PS-07)
Compound Sentence	We all know that the path one success is often times rough but with strong heart and firm ambitions, we shall overcome. (PS-02) Let us work together and renew our commitment to promote education as a fundamental right. (PS-05) We must ensure that our people can go about their daily lives without fear and our children can receive an education in a safe environment. (PS-07) The program also includes the distribution of food relief packs to parents and a talk about responsible parenthood. (PS-11)
Complex Sentence	We take inspiration from our fellow Filipinos which persevere to change the educational landscape in our country. (PS-02) As future leaders and builders of our nation, may you become persistent, determined and committed to

fight for peace security and stability. (PS-04)

My life is a testament of the power of a God whom we know by many names. (PS-10)

Simple sentence. A simple sentence is a sentence that consists of just one independent clause. To have an independent clause, it must contain a subject and a verb and express a complete thought. In the corpora that had been analyzed, majority of the Public Speeches of Vice President Sara Duterte were found using a simple sentence in conveying their message to the viewers. The used of simple words in a sentence enables the readers and the viewers to tailor the message with easily and comprehensively.

Education is all about nation building. (PS-2)

Today is a timely opportunity to renew our call to everyone. (PS-6)

We must prioritize peace and order. (PS-7)

Compound sentence. Another syntactic feature presented in the corpora according to types of sentences was a compound sentence. Compound sentences are the two independent clauses which had been underlined in the samples below, joined by a colon, semicolon or with a coordinating conjunction written in bold text. For as long as the two sentences are not dependent on each other, it is a compound sentence.

The corpora that were analyzed found out that most of the Public Speeches of Vice President Sara Duterte used compound sentence in conveying their ideas and message to the public.

Most compound sentences are used to add detail. Adding justification and further detail to what you are presenting, thus helping people to see the real message of the sentence.

Success is often times rough but with strong heart and firm ambitions, we shall overcome. (PS-02)

Let us work together and renew our commitment to promote education as a fundamental right. (PS-05)

We must ensure that our people can go about their daily lives without fear and our children can receive an education in a safe environment. (PS-07)

The program also includes the distribution of food relief packs to parents and a talk about responsible parenthood. (PS-11)

Complex sentence. The third type of sentence that can be traced in Public Speeches of Vice President Sara Duterte is the complex sentence. A complex sentence contains an independent clause and one or more dependent clauses. The independent clause either introduced by the markers which, that, when, that had been underlined.

We take inspiration from our fellow Filipinos which persevere to change the educational landscape in our country. (PS-2)

As future leaders and builders of our nation, may you become persistent, determined and committed to fight for peace security and stability. (PS-4)

My life is a testament of the power of a God whom we know by many names. (PS-10)

In the table presented, 3 out of 20 corpora used complex sentences in expressing or conveying the message of the Public Speeches. The used of complex sentences meant to tailor amount of information provided by adding a dependent clause to a simple sentence in order to emphasize particular aspects in their remarks. Persuasive Strategies employed in Vice President Sara Duterte's Public Speeches

Persuasive strategies play a vital role in public speeches as they help the speaker connect with the audience and convince them of their viewpoint. By using techniques like storytelling, appealing to emotions, and providing evidence, the speaker can effectively influence the audience's thoughts and opinions.

These strategies make the message more engaging and memorable, increasing the likelihood that the audience will agree with the speaker's perspective. Ultimately, persuasive strategies enable speakers to effectively communicate their ideas and inspire action among their listeners.

The art of persuasion was classified into three: ethos or the ethical appeal, logos or the logical appeal, and pathos or the emotional appeal. Ethos deals with the person character and goodness.

The utilization of person who possesses a highly reliable image to represent the information. The logical appeal dealt with the data or factual information of the ideas, concepts and thoughts. It could be a result of research or survey about topic. The emotional appeal dealt with the emotional aspect of the message. It often touches the emotion or feelings of the listener.

Table 2 presented that the Public Speeches of Vice President Sara Duterte employed persuasive strategies in presenting ideas to the mass public. To clearly understand, the first column presents the types of persuasive strategy.

The last column were the sample statements that show how the persuasive strategy has been utilized. The code PS which stands for Public Speeches followed by numbers stand as the code for each corpus.

Research Question 2: What persuasive strategies does Vice President Duterte employ in her speeches to influence political narratives and public perceptions?

Table 2. *Persuasive Strategies in in VP Sara Duterte’s Speeches*

<i>Persuasive Strategies</i>	<i>Sample Statement</i>
Ethical Appeal	<p>In our commitment to make our curriculum relevant to produce competent, job ready, active, and responsible citizens, we have launched the Matatag K-10 Curriculum. We have decongested the curriculum to focus on the development of the foundational skills. (PS-02)</p> <p>Together with our academic partners in all education levels let us remain committed to promoting our youth strong sense of nationalism so they can be part of a productive and responsible citizenry that will help chart the path of our nation’s growth. (PS-05)</p> <p>. To open up more opportunity and enable a better future for every Filipino child. I invite all our stakeholders, ambassadors, education ministers, and local and international partners to expand our relationship and collaboration (PS-06)</p>
Logical Appeal	<p>From approximately 11,000 napababa natin to 3,000 ang mga learning competencies. Sa key stages grade one to three dati seven subjects tayo binaba natin sa five subjects with the focus on math and reading and ang science natin papasok pag grade four. (PS-09)</p> <p>Research on the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic to school children around the world point to a significant learning loss. Our DEPED schools, divisions, and regional offices have prepared learning recovery plans to address learning gaps and accelerate students’ learning during this critical period. (PS-11)</p> <p>Through the promotion of alternative delivery modes, we were able to decrease the total number of dropouts due to teenage pregnancy and early marriage by 88.85%. We also the first learners convergence and launched the learner led and learner authored, learners declaration for the Matatag Agenda. (PS-02)</p> <p>We rolled out the national learning camp during the break to supplement the learning efforts to the previous school year. Last year’s national learning camp saw the involvement of 939,314 learners from grades 7 and 8. And 229,036 teachers from a total of 34,383 schools across 16 regions. (PS-02)</p>
Emotional Appeal	<p>. I salute your courage and dedication to your duty. We count on your relentless pursuit to defend our sovereignty, we can end the threat of insurgency, terrorism, and criminality and lead the way to a sustained peace and order situation in all our regions. (PS-01)</p> <p>I understand that you are afraid to go to school but you need to continue with your modules at home until you are ready to come to school. (PS-03)</p> <p>I am with you in forging a path towards progress even as you continue to live by the tenants that have guided you in your academic training and inspire you to pursue excellence as young leaders. (PS-05)</p>

Ethical Appeal. Ethos refers to the speaker’s character. Ethical appeal includes the practical wisdom, virtue, and goodwill of the speaker towards his or her audience. In table 2 under the ethical appeal the corpora were analyzed. The statements below emphasize that Vice President Sara Duterte utilized ethical appeal as a persuasive strategy in her Public Speeches in assuring the audience to provide quality and standardized education for all the Filipino citizen under her governance.

In our commitment to make our curriculum relevant to produce competent, job ready, active, and responsible citizens, we have launched the Matatag K-10 Curriculum. We have decongested the curriculum to focus on the development of the foundational skills. (PS-2)

Together with our academic partners in all education levels let us remain committed to promoting our youth strong sense of nationalism so they can be part of a productive and responsible citizenry that will help chart the path of our nation’s growth. (PS-5)

To open up more opportunity and enable a better future for every Filipino child. I invite all our stakeholders, ambassadors, education ministers, and local and international partners to expand our relationship and collaboration. (PS-6)

Logical Appeal. The second persuasive strategy present in the Vice President Sara’s speeches was the logical appeal or logos. Logos, as a persuasive strategy, centers on the rational appeal and the persuasion done using proof, or apparent proof, that was presented by the speaker itself. Logos can also be identified through the presence of warrant/justification, claims, data, and evidence/examples. The following statements were extracted from the corpora and it was found out that Vice President Sara Duterte uses logical appeal as a persuasive strategy by providing statistics to convey the present status of the Philippine Educational System to the mass audience.

From approximately 11,000 napababa natin to 3,000 ang mga learning competencies. Sa key stages grade one to three dati seven subjects tayo binaba natin sa five subjects with the focus on math and reading and ang science natin papasok pag grade four. (PS-9)

Another sample of logical appeal is the statement below from the Public Speech of Vice President Sara Duterte where she stated the effects of COVID-19 pandemic to education by presenting research that point out a significant learning loss around the world.

Research about the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic to school children around the world point to a significant learning loss. Our DEPED schools, divisions, and regional offices have prepared learning recovery plans to address learning gaps and accelerate students’ learning during this critical period. (PS-11)

Furthermore, below is another example of logical appeal. From the corpus coded as PS-2, the Vice President presented data on how the promotion of alternative delivery modes decreased the total number of dropouts due to teenage pregnancy and early marriage by

88.85%.

Through the promotion of alternative delivery modes, we were able to decrease the total number of dropouts due to teenage pregnancy and early marriage by 88.85%. We also conducted the first learners' convergence and launched the learner led and learner authored, learner's declaration for the Matatag Agenda. (PS-2)

Emotional Appeal. The last persuasive strategy emerged in Public Speeches of Vice President Sara Duterte is the pathos. Pathos usually refers to emotional appeal and condition the audience into a certain frame of mind. The speakers show identification with what the audience needs, values, and the desires of the intended receiver of the message. Pathos also touches the sense of security, love, guilt, greed, pity, humor, empathy, and fear of the rhetoric to the audience to persuade them to adhere, believe and consume the ideas that was presented in the public speeches.

I salute your courage and dedication to your duty. We count on your relentless pursuit to defend our sovereignty, we can end the threat of insurgency, terrorism, and criminality and lead the way to a sustained peace and order situation in all our regions. (PS-1)

Furthermore, below is another example of emotional appeal. From the corpus coded as PS-3, the Vice President shows empathy to students and persuade them to continue with their modules until they are ready to go back to school.

I understand that you are afraid to go to school but you need to continue with your modules at home until you are ready to come to school. (PS-3)

Another example of emotional appeal is the statement below from OVP Sara's public speech where she expresses that she is with them and inspire them to pursue excellence as young leaders.

I am with you in forging a path towards progress even as you continue to live by the tenants that have guided you in your academic training and inspire you to pursue excellence as young leaders. (PS-5)

Research Question 3: What ideologies can be generated from the public speeches of Vice President Sara Duterte?

In this part, it delves into the underlying ideologies that are embedded in Vice President Sara Duterte's Speeches. The analysis is based from the Ideological Interaction Theory of Van Dijk (2006) which states that ideologies are the ideas and belief system of a particular group of people defined from the multidisciplinary ways involving social, cognitive and discursive aspects. He further argues that ideologies are acquired, expressed and propagated in the society mainly in different forms of discourses such as texts and talks.

Table 3 probes the ideologies present in Vice President Sara Duterte's Public Speeches. It also includes the sample statement from the corpora.

Table 3. Ideologies in VP Sara Duterte's Speeches

<i>Political Ideologies</i>	<i>Sample Statements</i>
Acquired	Furthermore, we are actively involving communities and local governments in a collaborative effort to the education. There by securing a brighter future for our students. (PS-06) We can provide more digital opportunities to social economic growth and gender empowerment and thereby enable women to rise above any form of online violence affecting their mental and physical well-being. (PS-03)
Expressed	In accelerating the delivery of basic education services governance is key and change must start from within. From the establishments of the procurement strand last year, we have awarded 288 projects in the amount of 11.701 billion pesos. (PS-02)
Propagated	Consistent with our vision in the Matatag Agenda, we will continue to promote programs and uphold reforms that will nurture resilient mind-sets so that we can hone young Filipinos who have the capacity and resiliency to thrive in challenging circumstances. (PS-05)

Ideologies are acquired through socialization processes within various institutions such as family, education, media, and religious organizations. Individuals internalize dominant ideologies, including beliefs, values, norms, and stereotypes, through repeated exposure to discourses that reflect and reinforce these ideologies. This acquisition occurs through linguistic interactions, where individuals learn to interpret and make sense of the world based on the ideologies prevalent in their social environments. The acquired ideology which are extracted from the Public Speeches of Vice President Sara Duterte are as follows:

"Furthermore, we are actively involving communities and local governments in a collaborative effort to education. Thereby securing a brighter future for our students." (PS-06)

This statement reflects an ideological perspective that emphasizes collaboration, community involvement, and the role of education in securing a brighter future. The use of language such as "actively involving communities," "collaborative effort," and "securing a brighter future" conveys positive connotations associated with collective action, social responsibility, and optimism about the potential benefits of education. The utterance manifested an acquired ideology and this can be observed on how the statement perceived or acquired a need to secure brighter future for students.

"We can provide more digital opportunities to social economic growth and gender empowerment and thereby enable women to rise

above any form of online violence affecting their mental and physical well-being." (PS-03)

This statement reflects an ideological perspective that emphasizes the role of digital opportunities in promoting social economic growth, gender empowerment, and the well-being of women. The use of language such as "digital opportunities," "social economic growth," "gender empowerment," and "rise above any form of online violence" conveys positive connotations associated with technological advancement, gender equality, and resilience in the face of adversity. This is an example of acquired ideology since it is evident that the statement cites the perceived need to provide more digital opportunities to social economic growth and gender empowerment since there is an arising numbers of violence on women which affect their mental and physical well-being.

Once acquired, ideologies are expressed through language and discourse in communicative interactions. Individuals and groups use language strategically to convey, reinforce, or contest ideological positions. This expression can take various forms, including narratives, arguments, justifications, and evaluations, which serve to legitimize or challenge existing power structures and social hierarchies. Through linguistic strategies such as framing, persuasion, and manipulation, speakers shape perceptions and attitudes, influencing how ideologies are perceived and accepted by others.

"In accelerating the delivery of basic education services governance is key and change must start from within. From the establishments of the procurement strand last year, we have awarded 288 projects in the amount of 11.701 billion pesos." (PS-02)

The provided statement exemplifies an expressed ideology by articulating specific beliefs and values regarding governance, change, and resource allocation in the context of education service delivery. By asserting that "governance is key" in accelerating the delivery of basic education services, the statement reflects an ideological stance emphasizing the importance of effective leadership, transparency, and accountability in driving positive outcomes. Additionally, the assertion that "change must start from within" suggests a belief in the capacity of existing institutional structures to initiate and sustain reform efforts. Furthermore, the mention of awarding 288 projects totaling 11.701 billion pesos underscores an ideological commitment to resource mobilization and investment in education infrastructure, signaling a prioritization of education as a fundamental societal concern.

The propagation of ideologies involves the dissemination and reproduction of ideological beliefs and values across different social contexts. This process occurs through discursive practices that circulate ideologies within society, shaping public discourse, collective identities, and social practices. Institutions such as mass media, political institutions, educational systems, and cultural productions play key roles in propagating ideologies by framing issues, constructing narratives, and shaping public opinion. Additionally, interpersonal interactions and everyday discourses contribute to the spread and reinforcement of ideologies through social networks and interpersonal communication.

"Consistent with our vision in the Matatag Agenda, we will continue to promote programs and uphold reforms that will nurture resilient mind-sets so that we can hone young Filipinos who have the capacity and resiliency to thrive in challenging circumstances." (PS-05)

The statement provided exemplifies propagated ideology according to Van Dijk's framework because it represents a dissemination of specific beliefs and values to a broader audience. By emphasizing the promotion of programs and reforms aimed at nurturing resilient mindsets in young Filipinos, the statement seeks to propagate an ideological perspective that resilience is a desirable trait essential for success in challenging circumstances. Through the public speech, the statement communicates an underlying belief in the importance of resilience as a characteristic to be cultivated and developed in individuals, aligning with broader ideological narratives about personal growth, adaptability, and overcoming adversity. As such, the statement serves to propagate and reinforce a particular ideological stance on the value of resilience in shaping the attitudes and behaviors of young people, thus contributing to the dissemination of ideological beliefs within society.

Conclusions

This study has been carried out to shed light on the linguistic features of the speeches of VP Sara Duterte. At the same time, this study also dealt with exposing the ideologies concealed on VP Sara's speeches. This study also dealt with the unleashing of the persuasive strategies used by the Vice President. Discourse analysis findings and features are crucial and can be applied to the study of how language affects social context in the educational setting. The results of this study are essential specifically, it highlights the importance of authentic language used by incorporating real-world contexts to enhance listening, speaking, and comprehension skills.

Furthermore, it also contributes to vocabulary expansion, understanding the appropriate use of language in different social and cultural contexts by identifying relevant vocabulary items and phrases used. Allowing language teachers to integrate them into lessons and facilitate domain-specific language acquisition exposing learners to authentic language use in real-world context, moving beyond idealized textbook scenarios. Equip students with linguistic tools to authentic language use and foster crucial skills that transcends basic grammar and vocabulary.

Also, this study helps learners see how language shapes public opinion and influences decision-making which empowers them to participate meaningfully in discussions and express their ideas effectively. Moreover, develop the ability to question assumptions, evaluate evidence, and articulate their own viewpoints with clarity and reason: identify underlying biases, learners develop nuanced understanding of how language shapes public opinion

Additionally, the study emphasizes the teaching of pragmatic competence by focusing on the pragmatics of persuasive language, enabling learners to understand and use language appropriately in different social and professional settings. Moreover, it promotes critical thinking and media literacy skills by analyzing persuasive techniques employed, encouraging learners to evaluate information critically and become discerning consumers of language and media. Also, the research findings facilitate cross-cultural awareness, as the Vice President's speeches platforms attract a global audience.

On another note, this study might give the learners an engaging learning experience wherein they can learn about the linked connection between the language, power, and society. Learners who take part in text analysis were prompted to interpret, evaluate, and question the information being presented by generating thoughtful discussion about it. This then reflects that the analysis of text is a valuable trait for learners to have the skill to think strategically and evaluate information in any form: can be written or spoken text.

This research study has successfully attained its main objectives which were to explore the linguistic features present in VP Sara Duterte's speeches, the persuasive strategies used by the Vice President, and also with exposing the ideologies concealed on VP Sara's speeches. It has been shown that after data analysis, the materials have been presented and explanations have been provided in connection to the investigation of this study. In as much, this study is limited only to the analysis of 10 speeches, the following recommendations for future research are hereby presented.

Since this study focused on the analysis of linguistic features, ideologies, and persuasive strategies manifested in e-commerce livestreams, future research may still be conducted along this line. As such, future researchers may replicate this research study but with a larger dataset. It is highly recommended to increase the number of corpora to be used to verify the findings gathered. In connection, they are highly welcome to apply the same research approach or even try other approaches, or somehow, gather corpora from other websites or platforms.

Lastly, it is proposed that future researchers do a separate study on the same issue employing other methods or multiple approaches that are different from what is used in the current study. The researchers may also study the appropriate use and effect of language in political discourse and even metaphor employed by political leaders, examining the effects of these texts on readers or listeners. Researchers could research more the language used in political discourses and speeches by political figures outside institution and locality to learn more about how speeches affect the listeners. In connection, it would result the betterment of the current paper using the insights and findings that are to be gained from future studies.

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